

Attention to Virtualization: Making Network Digital Twins aware of Network Slicing

Alejandro Calvillo-Fernandez¹, Toni Dimitrovski^{2,4}, Milan Groshev³, Aditya Ganesh²,
Constantine Ayimba¹, and Antonio de la Oliva¹

¹Universidad Carlos III de Madrid

²Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research (TNO)

³The Laude Technology Company S.L.

⁴University of Twente

Abstract—In order to accommodate myriad disparate services, from legacy voice and data, to niche network applications for industry verticals, 6G networks are expected to heavily exploit the concept of network slicing introduced in 5G. However, the increased complexity of sliced networks amplifies the risk of configuration errors, necessitating the expanded use of Network Digital Twins (NDTs) for proactive service assurance. Legacy NDTs, are ill-suited to highly virtualized environments, as they fail to model the impact of virtualization on physical infrastructure and overlook long-term dependency effects. In this work, we highlight the performance impact of virtualization and introduce an attention-enhanced Graph Neural Networks (GNN)-based NDT to address these challenges. Our simulation results demonstrate that the proposed NDT framework significantly outperforms state-of-the-art models in accurately predicting service Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) across disparate use cases.

Index Terms—Virtualization, Attention, Network Digital Twin, Graph Neural Networks, Slicing.

I. INTRODUCTION

The diverse use cases envisioned for 6G demand a broad spectrum of differentiated services with disparate requirements on KPIs such as latency, throughput and reliability. One of the most effective mechanisms to accommodate these diverse needs while ensuring consistent Quality of Service (QoS) is network slicing [1]. This technique entails the creation of multiple, isolated virtual networks - referred to as “slices” - on a shared physical infrastructure. By partitioning resources into tailored, purpose-built logical networks, network slicing allows operators to optimize service delivery for different market segments.

Deploying network slices involves the creation of service function chains, which may include both virtualized and physical network elements. While Virtual Network Functions (VNFs)¹ can be dynamically instantiated, certain physical resources—such as radio resource units (RRUs)—cannot be virtualized and must be carefully allocated among slices. Managing this hybrid environment presents significant challenges. Changes made to provision new network slices can inadvertently affect ongoing services due to the complex interactions among shared infrastructure. To mitigate such risks,

it is crucial to evaluate configuration changes in a controlled staging environment before deploying them in production networks [1].

Recently, NDTs have emerged as cost-effective solutions for creating such staging environments [2, 3]. NDTs provide dynamic virtual representations of the physical network infrastructure. The reliability of NDTs is determined by how faithfully they mirror the underlying production network. In this regard, GNN-based NDTs have been shown to outperform other models [4–7].

Despite their advantages, state-of-the-art GNN-based NDTs do not address the **virtualization impact** in network slicing. Existing NDTs models treat network elements as isolated entities, failing to capture the resource contention that arises when VNFs share computing infrastructure [4]. Studies have shown that such contention can degrade performance by up to 40% compared to dedicated platforms [8, 9].

State-of-the-art GNN-based NDTs suffer from the **long-term dependencies**, where after multiple training rounds, the input layers of the neural networks receive insignificant gradient updates. This considerably slows the learning rate, limiting the ability of the model to adapt to evolving network conditions.

In order to address these challenges, in this article we propose an enhanced NDT framework that:

- 1) accounts for the virtualization impact by incorporating a virtualization-aware function in the network model and, through graph abstraction, captures its effects within network slices.
- 2) utilizes attention mechanisms within the GNN architecture to mitigate long-term dependencies, enabling more effective learning of complex relationships between network slices and physical computing resources.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first approach that explicitly considers the impact of virtualization on shared physical infrastructure in NDT modelling for sliced networks, while simultaneously addressing the performance limitations of existing GNN-based solutions.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows, we experimentally show the impact that virtualization has in network slicing in Section II. We provide background on GNNs and experimentally show the performance improvements of

¹In this article VNF is used as a compound term to include legacy virtualization using virtual machines and the more recent lightweight variant using containers.

Fig. 1. E2E delay under different number of deployed UPFs

self-attention in Section III. We present our attention-driven DT framework in Section IV together with the simulation findings. Finally, we present our lessons learned in Section V and conclusions in Section VI.

II. THE IMPACT OF VIRTUALIZATION

The network slicing concept is enabled by virtualization. Legacy VNFs were implemented as Virtual Machines (VMs), but recent evolution has led to Cloud-native Network Functions (CNF). In this approach, network functions are deployed as containerized cloud-native software that runs on Commercial Off The Shelf (COTS) servers. This presents a lightweight solution, with less overhead and faster execution times. However, performance penalties still arise when computing resources are shared among functions. To quantify these effects, we performed a series of experiments using Docker-containerized User Plane Functions (UPFs).

Our experimental environment emulated a CNF-based system on a SuperMicro COTS x86-64 server equipped with an Intel Xeon Gold 6130 processor (64 physical cores) and two Mellanox Technologies MT27710 Network Interface Cards (NICs), each supporting 10 Gbps bandwidth. CNFs can be deployed directly on bare metal or within VMs. For ease of management, we opted for the latter, hosting a VM with 8 pinned cores (16 threads) and directly attaching the two 10 Gbps NICs. To ensure an even distribution of computational load, we configured 8 queues per NIC and assigned CPU Interrupt Request (IRQ) classes to specific threads, balancing CPU usage across available cores. While this setup introduced some hypervisor overhead, its impact was minimized by ensuring the host operating system was not running any other workload. The VM was connected through the NICs to a separate physical server running the Trex traffic generator² to facilitate controlled testing.

The experimental scenarios involved deploying 1, 5, 10, 20 and 25 Docker-based Generic eXpress Data Path (XDP) UPF network functions in the VM under different traffic loads. For each experimental scenario, we generated traffic rates ranging from 0 to 1.8 Gpps (max capacity), split equally across the

Fig. 2. E2E losses under different number of deployed UPFs

number of deployed UPFs. Each combination of UPF and packet rate was repeated 10 times, with each experimental run lasting 60 seconds. Loss and delay metrics were obtained from observing the round-trip packet behaviour.

Fig. 1 illustrates a non-negligible increase in delay when multiple CNFs share the same computing resources. This effect is more pronounced under 0.3 Mpps when the interrupt handling of packets is prevalent due to low loads, and over 1.2 Mpps when CPU resources are reaching capacity. Similarly, Fig. 2 highlights that higher UPF concurrency accelerates system performance degradation and increases packet loss at a given traffic rate. This performance drop is primarily caused by resource contention, which intensifies as the number of concurrent UPFs increases. Prior research [9] attributes this degradation to memory bandwidth limitations and cache structure constraints, which can lead to CNF data structure evictions and packet replacements in cache memory.

As evident from Figs. 1 and 2, packet delays and loss rates (especially at high traffic loads) are significantly influenced by the number of UPFs processing traffic. These results expose *Problem 1: Virtualization impact in CNF*. Virtualization introduces a measurable performance penalty, which any network slicing model must account for to accurately predict QoS metrics and KPIs. Without incorporating these virtualization effects, network slicing models risk misrepresenting real-world performance and resource allocation dynamics.

III. GRAPH NEURAL NETWORK APPROACH

In this section, we examine the inherent limitations of GNNs, employed on best in class, state-of-the-art NDTs, in capturing long-term dependencies. GNNs have proven to be highly effective in modelling telecommunications networks by handling complex, graph-based relationships within network data [5]. Unlike traditional neural networks, suited for grid-structured data (e.g., images), GNNs iteratively aggregate and transform information from a node's neighbours to learn its representation. This process allows the model to capture both local and global structural information by exploiting the connectivity patterns of the graph.

Typically, GNNs employ the following process for each node:

²<https://trex-tgn.cisco.com/>

- **Message Passing:** the node receives messages from its neighbours, encapsulating their feature representations.
- **Aggregation:** the messages are combined using a permutation-invariant function (e.g., mean, sum, max).
- **Update:** the aggregated information is used to update the node’s feature representation through a neural network layer.

Standard GNN models face technical limitations in addressing *Problem 2: Long-Term Dependencies*. A key issue is the over-smoothing effect [10], where repeated message passing causes node features to become increasingly similar, eventually making them indistinguishable. Furthermore, these models often suffer from the problem of vanishing gradients during backpropagation, where the gradients diminish as they propagate through deeper layers. Furthermore, layers closer to the input may fail to update their weights effectively, slowing or even halting the learning process. Consequently, standard GNNs struggle to capture relationships between distant nodes in the graph.

To mitigate these limitations, advanced GNNs architectures were proposed such as Graph Attention Networks (GATs) [11], which incorporate self-attention [12] mechanisms to selectively emphasize critical graph connections. By computing attention coefficients, GATs weigh the relative importance of each neighbour during aggregation. We investigated how attention mechanisms mitigate the limitations on GNNs. Specifically, we evaluated the Gated Recurrent Units (GRUCells)-based GNN used in *RouteNet-Fermi* [4] against our hybrid model, which incorporates self-attention mechanisms [12]. Our approach consists of:

- **GraphSAGE** (SAmple and aggreGatE): a scalable GNN architecture that improves neighbourhood aggregation and generates node embeddings for large graphs.
- **GAT:** Enhances GNNs by incorporating self-attention, allowing the model to focus on the most relevant connections.

To compare the performance of these models, we trained both *RouteNet-Fermi* and our GraphSAGE+GAT model on a public network path analysis dataset³. We evaluated their performance using the following metrics: Mean Absolute Error (MAE) that measures the average prediction error, indicating overall accuracy; Mean Square Error (MSE) that penalizes large errors more heavily, highlighting each model’s ability to minimize significant deviations and coefficient of determination R^2 that indicates how well the model explains variance in the delay data, serving as a benchmark for predictive capability.

TABLE I
COMPARISON BETWEEN ROUTENET-FERMI AND A MODEL WITH
ATTENTION

Model	MAE	MSE	R^2
RouteNet-Fermi	0.248	30.38	0.970
GraphSAGE+GAT	0.026	0.003	0.95

³<https://github.com/ITU-AI-ML-in-5G-Challenge/ITU-ML5G-PS-002-SNOWYOWL-GNNNetworking-Challenge2022>

Table I summarizes the obtained results, demonstrating the performance improvements of our GraphSAGE+GAT model in terms of MAE and MSE. While the lower MAE (0.026 vs. 0.248) of our model reflects the improved consistency in minimizing average prediction errors, the significant reduction in MSE (0.003 vs. 30.38) highlights the impact of self-attention in mitigating large prediction errors. Concerning R^2 (0.95 vs. 0.970), the results indicate that RouteNet-Fermi aligns slightly better with overall dataset patterns. However, this difference is minimal (0.15), indicating that our model captures most of the variance in network delays. Overall, these results indicate that our GraphSAGE+GAT model achieves lower error metrics compared to the baseline.

RouteNet-Fermi employs GRUCells-based sequence modelling to enhance gradient propagation and manage sequential dependencies. However, this approach processes information sequentially, restricting its ability to model long-term dependencies effectively. In contrast, our GraphSAGE+GAT model, equipped with self-attention, can attend to all positions in the input simultaneously. This enables direct access to relevant information, regardless of its position in the graph, rather than relying solely on the most recent state. As a result, our hybrid approach demonstrates superior error minimization while maintaining high predictive capacity.

IV. ATTENTION TO VIRTUALIZATION: A FRAMEWORK FOR NETWORK SLICING

In this section, we present the technical foundation of our proposed framework for modelling sliced networks. Our approach leverages a NDT built on a GNN variant incorporating a self-attention mechanism. This enables a more accurate representation of the complex underlying architecture of network slicing.

A. Modelled Scenarios

A network slice tailored to a specific service may consist of CNFs, Physical Network Functions (PNFs), or a combination of both. To illustrate their impact on network performance, we analyse end-to-end latency between two endpoints over a single network hop across three scenarios:

In the first scenario, both endpoints are physical nodes. The total latency includes processing delays from the application layer down to the physical layer, network propagation delay, and processing delays at the receiving endpoint.

In the second scenario, one endpoint is a physical node, while the other is a containerized function hosted on a separate physical node. While the initial latency components remain the same, additional processing delays arise due to the virtualization layer (e.g., hypervisor or container engine) before reaching the containerized endpoint.

The third scenario involves two containerized functions as endpoints. Here, latency is influenced by virtualization overhead at both sender and receiver ends, as well as network propagation delay. The network propagation delay may also be impacted by virtualization if both VNFs are hosted on the same physical node.

Fig. 3. General Architecture figure.

B. NDT Model Framework

In order to create a NDT that faithfully reflects resource contention issue (*Problem 1*) and address the complexity of modelling modern networks (*Problem 2*), we propose the architecture shown in Fig. 3. This architecture enhances the IRTF-NMRG⁴ model by integrating a Management and Orchestrator (M&O) module into the control loop for lifecycle management of slices. The modelled scenarios provide a foundation for understanding the various latency factors associated with different combinations of PNFs and CNFs. In order to include these three scenarios into the model, we propose a two stage framework, consisting of: Graph Abstraction and Graph Aggregation.

1) *Graph Abstraction:* This stage encodes network properties into vectorized representations, using graphs that depict topological and relational information within the DT. The nodes in these graphs are classified as follows:

- **CNF nodes:** Represent flow states and virtual resource utilization per CNF.
- **Physical Nodes:** Reflect the status of resources on PNFs or the physical nodes hosting CNFs.
- **Edges:** Indicate the communication dependencies between nodes.

2) *Graph Aggregation:* This stage trains the GNN by learning from multiple input-output cases to establish correlations between features and QoS metrics. The GNN model employs an attention mechanism, where for each target node i , a

query vector is generated by linearly transforming the node's hidden state using a learnable projection matrix. The query encapsulates the node's characteristics, allowing it to "ask" how much information it should gather from each of its neighbours. Similarly, a key vector for neighbour node j is derived, representing the "response" to the query. The dot product between the query and the key gives an *attention score* that reflects the relevance of node j to the target node i . We can add the edge embedding between nodes i and j to enrich this attention score calculation. The value vector contains the actual information that the target node receives from the neighbour during the aggregation step.

The value vectors, weighted by the attention scores, are aggregated to update the target node's representation. This process is executed in parallel, for n numbers of "heads". All attention scores are concatenated to produce the final output for the target node.

C. Workflow

The M&O module initiates the slicing process by defining a service intent, such as: Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMMB) Video Streaming slice that targets very high data rates and wide coverage, a Massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC) Smart City application slice that needs to handle a large number of low-power Internet of Things (IoT) devices and an Ultra-High Reliability & Low Latency Communications (uRLLC) Industry 4.0 application slice that demands sub-millisecond latency and high reliability [13].

Once the intent is defined, the M&O generates initial configurations, which are evaluated within the NDT. The NDT

⁴<https://datatracker.ietf.org/doc/html/draft-irtf-nmrg-network-digital-twin-arch-05>

predicts the impact of these configurations on both existing slices and potential new slices using "what-if" scenario analysis. The self-attention mechanism ensures that the most relevant elements in the network graph are prioritized based on their influence on KPI such as latency and packet loss.

The analysis results are fed back to the M&O, which then orchestrates the slice deployment based on the predicted performance. As new configurations are applied, real-time data from the operational network is continuously fed back into the NDT (right side of Fig. 3), refining its accuracy by correcting discrepancies between predicted and observed behaviour.

D. Experimental Validation

To validate our framework, we conduct simulations to estimate end-to-end flow delay (in ms) under various network slicing conditions. We extend the OMNeT++ [14] simulator to support CNFs and PNFs by implementing an empirically derived function (based on our virtualization experiments in Section II) that adjusts the delay based on computational resource utilization, effectively capturing the impact of virtualization on network performance (*Problem 1*).

Our simulations consider diverse network topologies comprising 30 CNF nodes and 5 physical nodes. We evaluate three communication scenarios: CNF-CNF, Physical-to-Physical, and CNF-to-Physical. Traffic is generated to simulate multiple service types with different distributions, including Poisson – for bursty eMMB, Constant Bit Rate (CBR) or periodic for uRLLC. Table II shows our simulation parameters.

TABLE II
TRAFFIC PARAMETERS AND CPU/RAM USAGE CALCULATION

Parameters	Values
Policies	FIFO, SP, WFQ, DRR
Buffer Sizes (bytes)	8000, 16000, 32000, 64000
WFQ Weights	70, 20, 10; 33.3, 33.3, 33.4; 60, 30, 10; 80, 10, 10; 65, 25, 10
DRR Weights	60, 30, 10; 70, 25.5; 33.3, 33.3, 33.4; 50, 40, 10; 90, 5, 5
Link Capacity (kbps)	10000, 25000, 40000, 100000, 250000, 400000
Traffic Intensity (kbps)	Uniform(0,1) \times I, $I \in \{1000, 2000, 3000, 4000\}$
Packet Size Distribution	0, 500, 750, 1000, 1250, 1500
Time Distribution	Poisson, CBR, ON-OFF
Type of Service (ToS)	0, 1, 2
CPU Usage (VNF nodes)	Incremented by traffic intensity / 1000
RAM Usage (VNF nodes)	Incremented by traffic intensity / 100
CPU Usage (Physical hosts)	Incremented by traffic intensity / 1000
RAM Usage (Physical hosts)	Incremented by traffic intensity / 200

We process the data into a knowledge graph where each node contains features that describe the traffic flow, the virtual resource usage (for virtual nodes) and the physical resource usage (for physical nodes). Edges between nodes reflect connectivity and include attributes such as link capacity and scheduling policies.

In the modelling phase, we employ a GNN-based approach. We employ 70% of the generated data for training the model and 30% for testing. Our model combines a *GraphSAGE* for node embeddings and two *GATs* layers for the attention, with 4 heads, and 32 hidden layers. We optimize the model using

Adam employing a learning rate of 0.001 and MSE as the loss function.

Fig. 4 presents the network delay prediction results of two different NDT approaches based on GNNs: a standard Message Passing GNN, used in best-in-class NDTs [5], and our proposed GNN with attention. The diagram integrates three network slices corresponding to distinct latency requirements: uRLLC for near-instantaneous communication (notice the curve shape due to the strict requirements), mMTC where precise control loop timing is necessary, and eMMB where high throughput is prioritized over strict latency control [13].

The results show that our attention-based GNN achieves predictions that closely align with the ideal performance, reflecting enhanced consistency and reduced variance in delay estimates. Moreover, it does not underestimate delays, thereby favouring the provisioning of superfluous resources rather than allocating insufficient resources that may result in service degradation or disruption. In contrast, the standard Message Passing GNN exhibits greater variance in its predictions. These findings confirm that attention mechanisms effectively mitigate *Problem 2* by focusing on relevant features, thereby enhancing prediction precision.

V. CHALLENGES AND FUTURE WORK

Our study highlights the necessity of enhancing NDTs by integrating both virtualization impact, and attention mechanisms to improve predictive capabilities. A significant challenge in developing this framework is the absence of datasets that accurately capture the complexity of real-world virtualized networks. Addressing this limitation requires extending simulation platforms, such as OMNeT++, with custom modules to model CNFs, lifecycle states, and realistic latency constraints. To complement synthetic datasets, real-time telemetry from virtualization platforms like Kubernetes and OpenStack can provide fine-grained insights into resource utilization and network performance. However, integrating this data into NDTs requires a continuous deployment pipeline to ensure models remain up to date, allowing for iterative refinements and adaptive learning.

A key scalability challenge in GNN-based NDTs arises from the quadratic growth of pairwise attention computations in GATs, limiting their applicability in large-scale network scenarios. Hierarchical GNN architectures [15] address this issue by partitioning large graphs into structured subgraphs, applying attention selectively at higher levels of abstraction to mitigate computational overhead. Our future work will focus on implementing such hierarchical GNNs and exploring transformer-based architectures to enhance scalability in expansive network environments.

Besides scalability, trust and explainability remain critical for operators adopting GNN-based NDTs. The "black box" nature of deep learning models raises concerns regarding reliability and compliance with Service Level Agreements (SLAs). While attention mechanisms offer some interpretability by highlighting influential nodes and edges, further research is needed to enhance transparency and build confidence in these predictive models.

Fig. 4. Measured (Ground truth) delay vs Predicted Delay CDFs of network delay across three slices using two GNN models. Attention-based GNN prediction closely follow the S-shaped ground truth CDFs across uRLLC, mMTC, and eMBB. In contrast, Standard GNN predictions show higher bias, underscoring the advantage of the attention mechanism.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this article, we present a framework for the remediation of two key challenges present in the state-of-the-art NDTs. We demonstrated that the incorporation of virtualization aspects and graph attention mechanisms complements the management architecture of the underlying network. Our results demonstrate that the proposed NDT model consistently outperforms existing techniques in predicting KPIs across diverse service classes, highlighting its adaptability to evolving network conditions. The ability of the attention mechanism to adapt to changing network patterns over time is reflected in this result. This model thus provides an NDT that is more robust to the sources of variance seen in real communication networks, and makes for a reliable inference tool for M&O of network slices.

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VIII. BIOGRAPHY SECTION

Alejandro Calvillo-Fernandez (M.Sc.’2024): He is currently a Ph.D. student at Universidad Carlos III de Madrid.

Toni Dimitrovski (M.Sc.’2016): He is currently a Ph.D. student at the University of Twente and a Research Scientist at TNO.

Milan Groshev (M.Sc.’2016, Ph.D.’2022): He is currently a Senior Researcher at Laude Tech.

Constantine Ayimba (M.Sc.’2016, Ph.D.’2022): He is currently a post-doctoral researcher at Universidad Carlos III de Madrid.

Aditya Ganesh (M.Sc.’2023): He is a Research Scientist at TNO.

Antonio de la Oliva (M.Sc.’2004, Ph.D.’2008): He is currently an associate professor at Universidad Carlos III de Madrid.